

**AFRICANITIES IN OPENING: BLACKGOGICAL PROPOSALS IN DANCE FOR CEI
JARDIM RODOLFO PIRANI**

AFRICANIDADES EN APERTURA: PROPUESTAS PRETAGÓGICAS DE DANZA PARA EL CEI
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Abstract

This article presents a pedagogical practical proposition, using the Africanities' markers and Blackgogy's operative concepts as an alternative for theoretical and methodological reference to the approach of ethnical-racial relations in dance to develop children education in Kindergarten, specifically from three to four years-old children at CEI Jardim Rodolfo Pirani in São Mateus' neighborhood, in São Paulo's East zone. Dialoguing with the reflections of Sandra Petit (2015), Geranilde Silva (2019) and based on Brazilian Common National Curricular Basis (2017) this article presents a pedagogical proposal for the institution, when discussing and reflecting on possible contents to be developed within the institution.

Keywords: Dance; Anti-racist Education; Early Childhood Education; Pedagogical Practices.

Resumen

Este artículo presenta una propuesta de práctica pedagógica, utilizando los marcadores de africanidad y conceptos operativos de la Pretagogía, como referencia teórico-metodológica alternativa en el abordaje de las relaciones étnico-raciales en la danza para desarrollar la formación de los niños de la Escuela Infantil, específicamente los de tres a cuatro años del CEI Jardim Rodolfo Pirani en el barrio de São Mateus, en la Zona Este, en el municipio de São Paulo. Dialogando con las reflexiones de Sandra Petit (2015), Geranilde Silva (2019) y a partir de la Base Curricular Común Nacional (2017), presenta una propuesta pretagógica para la institución, al reflexionar y debatir sobre posibles contenidos a desarrollar.

Palabras clave: Danza; Educación Antirracista; Educación para la primera infância; Prácticas Pedagógicas.

Resumo

Este artigo apresenta uma proposição de prática pedagógica, utilizando os marcadores das africanidades e conceitos operatórios da Pretagogia, como alternativa de referencial teórico-

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metodológico na abordagem das relações étnico-raciais em dança para desenvolver a formação de crianças do Ensino Infantil, em específico de três a quatro anos do Centro de Educação Infantil Jardim Rodolfo Pirani no bairro de São Mateus, na Zona Leste, do município de São Paulo. Dialogando com as reflexões de Sandra Petit (2015), Geranilde Silva (2019) e fundamentada na Base Nacional Comum Curricular (2017), apresenta uma proposta pretagógica para a instituição, quando reflete e debate sobre possíveis conteúdos a serem desenvolvidos.

Palavras-chaves: Dança; Educação Antirracista; Educação Infantil; Práticas Pedagógicas.

Introduction

In the context of early childhood education in Brazil, especially in Early Childhood Centers (CEIs) located in peripheral areas, it is essential to understand the diversity of nationalities and ideologies in the construction of learning. In this way, this article presents the stages of the investigation carried out at the CEI Jardim Rodolfo Pirani³, located in the São Mateus region, within the Conjunto Promorar Rio Claro, in the municipality of São Paulo, from the end of the first semester of 2019.

The first step of this research was carried out on June 3, 2019, through an invitation from the cultural support organization Associação Doce Saber. This invitation was made so that the first author of this article could speak at a meeting with the teachers at CEI Jardim Rodolfo Pirani and present the relevance of implementing Laws 10.639/2003 and 11.645/2008, which are legislative milestones in Brazil that aim to promote inclusion and recognition of the country's ethnic-cultural diversity. Law 10.639/2003 makes it compulsory to teach Afro-Brazilian history and culture in schools, while Law 11.645/2008 also includes the teaching of indigenous history and culture. Both laws are fundamental to combating structural racism and promoting the appreciation of the contribution of these groups to the formation of national identity.

The invitation was necessary because the number of immigrant children from Angola, Senegal and Haiti enrolling in the school was growing, and the teachers were not finding effective mechanisms to include the provisions of these laws within the institution. Because some of the children didn't speak Brazilian Portuguese, they became introspective and mostly didn't want to take part in the proposed activities.

³ CEI Jardim Rodolfo Pirani is an Early Childhood Education Center that is part of the São Mateus Regional Directorate of Education. It is located at Rua Cinira Polônio, number 20 in Conjunto Promorar Rio Claro, with opening hours from 7am to 5pm. The activity took place from October 8 to 31, 2019, from 9am to 12pm.

After two months there was another invitation, but to develop and apply an artistic-educational proposal, which was entitled "Dances and Playful Games in Early Childhood Education". With this in mind, a triad of activities was proposed: a drawing session (Bino and Fino, Guilhermina and Candelário), and games from countries such as Angola, Senegal and Haiti. As an example of games from these countries, we can mention the game of rolling hula hoops. In addition to the drawing session and the cycle of games, there was also a proposal to learn songs from the countries mentioned in conjunction with dance practices.

Following the activities carried out at CEI Jardim Rodolfo Pirani, it was possible to reflect on the importance of developing content to ensure a multicultural and inclusive education from early childhood onwards. The objectives of these activities were to identify, encourage and incorporate new perspectives of awareness in the world, so that Brazilian children, from an early age, have contact with the languages spoken on the African continent and recognize the importance of these populations in everyday life, especially in pedagogical practices. It is important to emphasize that African cultural representations are less portrayed in society than European ones. But how can we develop pedagogical approaches that are in tune with Africanities? Which Brazilian national documents can serve as a basis for this?

In order to develop pedagogical thinking in line with Africanities, it is important to take into account some Brazilian national documents that provide guidelines for early childhood education. One of these documents is the National Common Core Curriculum (BNCC), which establishes the knowledge, skills and abilities that should be developed throughout basic education, including early childhood education. The BNCC emphasizes the importance of valuing cultural diversity and promoting inclusive pedagogical practices, thus allowing for the incorporation of Africanities.

The BNCC (Brasil, 2017, p. 41) points out that a:

Early Childhood Education needs to promote experiences in which children can make observations, manipulate objects, investigate and explain their surroundings, raise hypotheses and consult sources of information to find answers to their curiosities and questions (Brasil, 2017, p. 41).

We can see the importance of fulfilling a Comprehensive Education, i.e. the school must provide the child with a leading role through the development of autonomy and other skills based on and elucidated within this legal document of Brazilian education.

In addition, the BNCC (Brasil, 2017, p. 25) reiterates that children need to go through and develop the ten general competencies of Basic Education, taking into account the six learning and development rights, which are: living together, playing, participating, exploring, expressing and getting to know each other, constituting the axes of Early Childhood Education. From the perspective of play, the BNCC (Brasil, 2017, p. 36) points out that children should

Playing every day in different ways, in different spaces and times, with different partners (children and adults), expanding and diversifying their access to cultural productions, their knowledge, their imagination, their creativity, their emotional, bodily, sensory, expressive, cognitive, social and relational experiences (Brasil, 2017, p. 36).

Using the words imagination, creativity, emotional, bodily, sensory, expressive and social experiences, the BNCC (Brasil, 2017) addresses the topic of play in a comprehensive and objective manner. In this case, the specificities of children must be taken into account, since, among the six learning rights mentioned, we have "knowing oneself", and play is supported by this realization when dealing with children in and out of the school environment.

It is in the act of playing that children strengthen their imagination and interpret what they observe, perceive and interact with the world and others. Play provides socialization processes, awakening their creativity and developing motor, cognitive, cultural and communicative skills. By providing an environment conducive to play, the state assumes responsibility for ensuring the healthy development of children, since they are active members of society. From birth, children need proper education and care so that they can develop.

Recognizing the importance of play, the state must promote public policies that ensure spaces and opportunities for children to play. This involves creating and maintaining safe and adequate parks, squares and leisure areas, as well as including play and recreational activities in school curricula.

The State's duty towards Early Childhood Education is stated in Art. 227 of the Magna Carta, popularly known as the Citizen Constitution (Brasil, 1988), which states that:

it is the duty of the family, society and the State to ensure children and adolescents, with absolute priority, the right to life, health, food, education, leisure, vocational training, culture, dignity, respect, freedom and family and community life, as well as to protect them from all forms of neglect, discrimination, exploitation, violence, cruelty and oppression (Brasil, 1988).

Based on these conceptions, in order to promote the integral development of children, it is essential that they are also guaranteed the right to know their ancestry and implement perspectives for the future based on their own history. It is in this sense that it can be said that the school curriculum generates identities, representations and notions of the world, so the problem is not only in the propagation of content, but when the bias of black representation is not validated, such learning is delegitimized because its place is not recognized in school and, above all, in the teacher training process.

In this logic, articulating the school curriculum with decolonized pedagogical practices provides children with opportunities beyond protagonism, enhancing their identities as subjects of knowledge, cultures and belonging to society. Therefore, it is in the physical educational space that children are able to establish relationships with themselves, the world and people. However, the school space must present possibilities that portray multiple cultures and the social environment in which the child is inserted. In other words, it should offer linguistic, cognitive and motor challenges that will help them develop their individual and community potential.

For psychiatrist and philosopher Frantz Omar Fanon (2022, p. 26), decolonization provides multiple strategies for concepts that have historically been guided by a Eurocentric vision, in other words, centered on European and colonized values. In other words, decolonization leads to a new way of perceiving what is presented as knowledge beyond the systematization of a curriculum, exposing the plurality of conceptions of being and knowing.

Decolonization never goes unnoticed because it affects being, it fundamentally changes being, it transforms spectators burdened with inessentiality into privileged actors, harvested in an almost grandiose way by the living wheel of history. It introduces into being a rhythm of its own, transmitted by new men, a new language, a new humanity (Fanon, 2022, p. 26).

Although Brazil ceased to be a colony of Portugal in 1822, even today, the standard within Brazilian education and society remains based on Eurocentrism. In this line of reasoning, the Argentine semiotician Walter Mignolo (2003) states that

(...) Eurocentrism therefore becomes a metaphor to describe the coloniality of power, from the perspective of subalternity. From an epistemological perspective, local European knowledge and histories were seen as global

projects, from the dream of an *Orbis universalis christianus* to Hegel's belief in a universal history, narrated from a perspective that places Europe as the point of reference and arrival. (Mignolo, 2003, p. 41)

This Eurocentric reference reproduces concepts that silence and erase those who do not have the opportunity to tell their own story. It is therefore difficult to talk about the construction and production of new perspectives without referring to the power structures that are established in society, be they economic, political or ideological, because it is in reference to power structures. And in order to counter these power structures, moving beyond telling someone else's story allows this story to be decreed as true by the voice of a third party and perpetuated with stereotypes. In this way, the colonizer destroys the imaginary of the other, as well as implementing subalternization through epistemic violence, reaffirming their own imaginary.

Education

Thinking about an education with afro-referenced perspectives means rethinking the teacher-student relationship that promotes Traditional Pedagogy. According to Fusari and Ferraz (2010, p. 27), this pedagogy emerged around the 19th century, with the aim of educating to literate and qualify the student to exercise a certain profession that would generate a financial return according to the market.

In this perspective, the main characteristic is a capitalist, standardized and reproductive educational model, with a view to an educational project for the training of students, with a pre-established national identity that overrides the issue of individuality to the detriment of the collective, in which the intention is to annul the "different", under the assumption that it deviates from socially imposed standards. This contributes to the distance between the teaching-learning process and the students' everyday practices.

However, even with the creation of multiple constructivist educational thoughts, Traditional Pedagogy is still the most applied in education networks in Brazil, so it is clear the problems and contradictions that exist in the axis of education.

In this circumstance, applying an Afroreferenced Pedagogy as a tool to unite education and the history of the subjects who are inserted in a given place, provides children with the state of recognizing and developing belonging, so that they understand

their role in the school environment and in the world. This education, containing a pedagogical interdisciplinarity, occupies the discourse as a responsible and possible way to reduce inequalities, understanding the social and subjective issues that interfere with student performance and thus their permanence in the educational institution. Since ensuring access to school is the responsibility of the state and promoting the child's belonging is the duty of the school institution, or as Aza Njeri says⁴ :

I therefore believe that incorporating the contributions of non-whites to humanity into pedagogical practice and expanding it through non-Eurocentric perspectives - in terms of history, culture, language, politics, economics, technology and science - makes the teaching-learning process and school socialization less traumatic, more plural and emancipatory. (Njeri, 2019)

These perspectives present a concern with debates on ethnic-racial issues in contemporary times, since society, as well as schools, are still persuaded and perpetuate the myth of racial democracy, thus distancing themselves from the impacts it ends up having on the lives of each child.

Historically speaking, even with the end of slavery, the black population was constantly placed on the margins of Brazilian society. This is still an issue today, even though there are numerous actions by the black movement in all Brazilian states. In the 19th and 20th centuries, disparaging and racist theories emerged in the Americas and Europe to maintain the idealization of the black population as inferior, deconstructing their identity. These discourses were also perpetuated in the school environment, in subjects such as History, where black people are only seen as slaves, without discussing the pre-abolition, during and post-abolition periods of slavery. However, through the black movements, the fight against racial discrimination in all spheres was generated and identity relations with Africans and their descendants flourished.

Through the revalorization of black people, especially children, it recognizes that human identity is conceived in community, based on its relationship with the other and with the cultural elements that distinguish one from the other. As Muniz Sodré (2015) states when he reiterates that: "To say human identity is to designate a complex

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relationship that links the subject to a continuous framework of references, constituted by the intersection of their individual history with that of the group in which they live" (Sodré, 2015, p. 39).

Similarly, the school plays a fundamental role in promoting dialog and the exchange of knowledge and experiences between individuals. It is in this environment that the first contacts with cultural diversity are established, including Afro-Brazilian and African culture, which is already part of the school curriculum.

By allowing and encouraging discussion and reflection on these different cultural conceptions, the school provides opportunities for confrontations to take place in a constructive way. It is through these confrontations that we can broaden our understanding and acceptance of other cultures. The act of generating these confrontations does not necessarily mean creating conflicts, but creating a space for open dialog, where different perspectives can be expressed and discussed in a respectful manner. It is through this dialog that we can break down stereotypes and prejudices, promoting a greater understanding and appreciation of cultural diversity.

By integrating Afro-Brazilian and African culture into the school curriculum, the school recognizes the importance and relevance of these cultures for children's education. This inclusion allows students to have contact with different cultural manifestations, contributing to a more plural and enriching education. However, it is in the act of generating these confrontations that the understanding and acceptance of other conceptions of cultures is corroborated.

A brief look at the progress made by the black movement brings us to the approval and implementation of Law 10.639 (Brasil, 2003), sanctioned on January 9, 2003 by the President of the Republic Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva, which amends Law 9.394 (Brasil, 1996), of December 20, 1996. In this way, the teaching of Afro-Brazilian and African History and Culture became compulsory, but the implementation of this law cannot be seen as a mere load of content. Such a law can and should be a stimulating foundation for schools in the debate and applicability of the subject, as it ensures that teachers have the guarantee and confidence to discuss, since there is a law that generates support for educational chains.

Based on the above, it is worth understanding that, especially in the school environment, there are images representing different societies. However, the racial issue in Brazil permeates a complex field, given that some representations gain greater visibility

and thus come to be seen as a reference for a standard. This sustains multiple inequalities through an un verbalized pact to maintain the privileges of whiteness. According to Cida Bento (2014), there is a self-preservation as a benefited group through the narcissistic pact, as explained by the author in the following terms:

The silence, the omission, the distortion of the place of whites in the situation of racial inequalities in Brazil has a strong narcissistic component, of self-preservation, because it is accompanied by a heavy investment in placing this group as a reference group for the human condition. (Bento, 2014, p. 30)

In this sense, critically analyzing the fact that Brazilian education, specifically in the early childhood education sector, still presents these images that were and are constructed and followed through the gaze of the idealized European. As a consequence, this leads to the production of meanings of what is and isn't the "standard". This appearance produces new meanings and consequences in society and in the children's identity process.

The practice of pressure to whiten is not something recent in Brazilian society, since Brazil was the first country in Latin America to establish a eugenic society in 1918, administered by Renato Kehl (1889-1974). In addition, the Constitutions of 1934 and 1937 contain several articles that defend eugenic concepts. For example, Article 138 of the 1934 Constitution:

Art. 138 - It shall be incumbent upon the Union, the States and the Municipalities, under the terms of their respective laws: b) to encourage eugenic education; f) to adopt legislative and administrative measures aimed at restricting infant morality and morbidity; and of social hygiene, which prevent the spread of transmissible diseases; g) to take care of mental hygiene and encourage the fight against social poisons. (Brasil, 1934)

Therefore, thinking about the education of black children is one of the most pending problems in our society, and as we saw in the 1934 Constitution, a fact rooted in the law that constituted the vision of Brazilian society in the 1930s. Given that racial inequalities are accentuated in various educational institutions and even in the law prior to the current one, it is suggested that teachers ask themselves: what materials and content are used in their classes for children?

Since Brazilian classrooms have a responsibility to present an interdisciplinary and plural education in accordance with the main basic education documents. Since everyone has the right to be recognized in any teaching materials, one of the relevant points that

must be taken into account is that learning must be constantly strengthened in a democratic and inclusive way, respecting and valuing cultural diversity and reprimanding discriminatory practices (Brasil, 2017, p. 14).

Methodological Procedures

The methodological procedures adopted in this dance study are characterized as theoretical-practical, with a qualitative approach. The research was supported by previous studies carried out by other authors investigating decolonial practices in dance teaching and early childhood education, such as Sheila Perina de Souza and the Luderê Afro Lúdico Collective. In order to obtain relevant information, we used a manual search method in the databases, with the aim of analyzing possible ways of applying Africanities using Afro-referenced materials.

The main objective was to select and explore studies that fully met the research proposal, especially considering that the act of playing was incorporated as a strategy to create a playful and welcoming environment, stimulating children's trust and participation. One of the theoretical and practical reflections chosen was blackgogy which, according to Sandra Petit (2015) and Geranilde Silva (2019), is an educational approach that focuses on self-directed learning and student autonomy. It emerged as a response to the need to recognize and value the experiences, knowledge and cultures of black and marginalized communities, rejecting traditional educational approaches that tend to be Eurocentric and exclusionary. Furthermore, based on the thinking of Sandra Petit and Geranilde Silva, Pretagogy recognizes the importance of representativeness and the inclusion of non-dominant perspectives in the school curriculum, thus seeking to promote a more equitable and transformative education. On this basis, this educational approach has been adopted as a tool for implementing Laws 10.639/03 and 11.645/08 in the school environment and applying a curriculum from an Afro-referenced perspective.

Results and discussion

Based on the results found, it was possible to verify the paths of study selected for the final analysis. For each meeting, a chart was created linking the "Markers of Africanness" and the "Operational Concepts". In addition, the procedures for each lesson were described. This approach allowed for the development of the children's integral formation, based on knowledge and practices of corporeality, including games from different African countries and Jongo - Circular Dance - which is part of Afro-Brazilian culture.

As for the analysis, this study adopted a qualitative approach to understand the results of the application of Afro-referenced content and the impact of Africanness on bodily practice, considering notions of the world. Initially, we mapped out practices that could be used in blackgogy and researched the children's nationalities.

Through this analysis, it was possible to see that each "Africanities Marker" enables interdisciplinarity with the proposed theme, making it possible to identify historical and cultural links with the African continent. This strengthens the school curriculum by promoting a sense of belonging in children and also helps in the development of teachers, especially when they are white educators.

Chart 1: Markers of Africanness.

History of my name	Afro Dance
History of my lineage, including aggregates	Afro hair (curly/curly/curly) - bodily practices of affirmation and denial of diacritical black features
Myths/legends/the act of telling/ valuing storytelling	Representation of Africa/Relations with Africa
Stories of my place of belonging/community/territorialities and black deterritorialities (movements of geographical, bodily and symbolic displacement)	Blackness - Strength and resistance
Flavors of my childhood - dishes, ways of eating and the value of food	Handicrafts
Black people who are references in my family and community and black people who are references in the world who are significant to me	Other technologies
symbolologies of circularity/cyclical times and nature	Family values/philosophy
mestras and mesteras negras/negros (of black culture)	Racism (perpetrated and suffered)
Black writings	Ways of living together/Solidarity ties/Community relations
Healing/health practices	Relationship with nature

Significant "black" smells	Black religiosity
My family's Afro festivals and today's festivals	Relationship with older women and men/Seniority (respect for older people)
Mythical places and Afro-marker territories (invested by blackness)	Afro vocabulary/Forms of speech
Songs/Ringtones/Rhythms/Afro Style	Relationship with the ground (experiential and symbolic)
Initiation practices and values/Transmission and teaching rites	Other bodily practices (traditional games, games and others)

Source: Petit and Alves (2015).

In the research, it was decided to explore the relationship of belonging, including Afro-descendant self-recognition for those who have this ethnic-racial identity. In addition, we sought to understand the social place of black people, which allows for a better understanding and identification of the naturalized racism present in society.

A central aspect of the research approach was the promotion of active participation by those involved, as opposed to sitting in the classroom. We highlight the use of music and songs from African countries (Angola, Senegal and Haiti) as a support for a practical and applicable way of promoting the implementation of laws 10.639/03 and 11.645/08. These songs play a fundamental role as a starting point for understanding the Afro-Brazilian worldview and for recognizing the African and Afro-Brazilian culture present in children's daily lives, which often goes unnoticed.

The lyrics of these songs are a valuable source of research in the classroom, allowing students to learn about the history and roots of black populations. By exploring these lyrics, students have the opportunity to delve into the culture, traditions and experiences of communities of African descent. This contributes to the appreciation of ethnic-cultural diversity, providing a sensory and emotional experience, involving the children more deeply with the themes addressed. Through rhythm and lyrics, they connect in an emotional way with Afro-Brazilian culture.

In addition, circularity in the way knowledge is assimilated and accommodated in a non-fragmented way was a crucial aspect of the research. We sought to establish connections between different areas of knowledge and dance, stimulating a more playful understanding.

The importance of children playing with elements of nature for their development is wide and varied. When they come into contact with plants and clay, these activities provide a series of benefits for their physical, mental, emotional and social growth. By

playing with plants, they have the opportunity to directly experience contact with nature and develop a sense of responsibility in caring for it.

Playing with clay and other natural substances stimulates children's creativity and imagination. They can mold and create different shapes, experiment with textures and colors, and express themselves artistically.

Interaction with natural elements also promotes children's social development. By playing together in natural environments, they learn to share, cooperate and solve problems as a group. It also creates a space for interaction and exchange between children and the community, strengthening social ties and promoting a sense of belonging and identity.

As the classes progressed, it became clear within the research that educational institutions play a fundamental role in the reflection and education of children, and should include themes in their curriculum that allow them to work with these cultures. We also recognized the importance of promoting discussions between teachers, staff, mothers and fathers about different ways of understanding cultural recognition and its relevance in the formation of critical citizens, capable of combating prejudice and racism, valuing the various cultural manifestations.

It was clear that Pretagogy needs to be present in the school's daily routine throughout the year, as a constant struggle, seeking to break down paradigms and promote cultural recognition. The school needs to commit to addressing these issues consistently and continuously, rather than as a one-off issue.

It is essential to invest in training and education for teachers, so that they feel confident and prepared to deal with these issues properly. In addition, it is essential to provide a welcoming, safe and inclusive school environment, where different cultural expressions are valued and respected.

Within the context of the markers of Africanness, during the process I realized that the children developed better when using elements of nature, dance and musicality in educational practices.

To connect with the operative concept of spirituality, the symbologies of circularity and the cycles of nature were used through games and dances. Exploring the way of living together, the bonds of solidarity and community relations, I worked on the sense of

belonging in different spaces of the institution, such as the classroom, the garden and the cafeteria.

In presenting Africa and its relations, a didactic approach was developed at CEI Jardim Rodolfo Pirani using drawings and animated content. In addition, other body practices were explored, such as traditional games and plays, to work on the operative concept of ancestry and initiatory processes, using music as a dynamic of guided gestures and, later, jongo body movements.

In order to approach Afro music, singing, playing, rhythms and styles, I explored the concept of transversality, studying different African musical manifestations in various countries.

At the same time, Pretagogy presents a second framework with operational concepts and their cross-cutting dimensions, going beyond traditional disciplines.

Chart 2: Operative concepts.

Operative concepts	Forms of operationalization, dimensions
Belonging	Experiences, contacts, empathy, information, connections, bodily practices, artistic-cultural practices
Transversality	Transdisciplinarity, diversity of language and literacy, possible skills promoted: uniqueness, creativity, joy. Bringing together dimensions: play, aesthetics and ethics
Spirituality	Relationship with the cosmos, with nature
Ancestry and Initiation Processes	Lineage(s), temporality, ritual symbolism, being a community
Didactic production	It involves African worldview values, encourages authorship/co-authorship and can generate new pedagogical goals.

Source: Petit and Alves (2015).

These overviews were developed to link the blackgogy activities. However, it requires the creativity and readiness of educators to interweave the proposals made in Débora Alfaia da Cunha's book "African games for cultural education", overcoming the barriers of the school and the Eurocentric curriculum in force in the institutions.

This intertwining makes Africanized praxis show that it is possible to rethink teaching-learning logics and especially the teacher-student relationship, adding values that consolidate children's integral learning. It is through community interaction, when children live, relate, breathe slowly, delight, run and jump, that they learn to assimilate and accommodate their conceptions of the world. This interaction with the community provides deeper learning, rooted in their reality and culture, allowing them to internalize and adapt their own worldviews.

In short, combining the panoramas of blackgogy with the book's proposals on African play offers an opportunity to rethink teaching practices, strengthen the relationship between teacher and student and enrich children's holistic learning. By adopting a more inclusive and culturally diverse approach, education can become more relevant, meaningful and aligned with students' realities.

Final considerations

Given the results obtained in this research study and the persistence of Traditional Pedagogy in CEIs, the need to rethink pedagogical practices is evident. The application of Afroreferenced Pedagogy appears as an alternative for uniting education and the history of the subjects, providing recognition and the development of the children's sense of belonging. And this idea takes shape from the experiences lived in the classrooms to the data collected from the legal education documents that served as support. It can be seen that, although educational practices have been restructured, the application of a decolonial methodology is a process that requires continuous improvement in educational institutions, demanding a daily exercise of reconfiguration, valorization and inclusion. The approaches that contemplate Laws 10.639/03 and 11.645/08 are still in the process of being applied.

In this context, over the course of this study, we gradually built up a new layer of understanding of the processes of learning and recognizing each individual's history. Through the process of mutual development with the children, I became part of the community and gained my own understanding of the "Africanities of openness". It is important to point out that one of the main obstacles to progress in the field of education is the distance between the law and its effectiveness, due to the lack of teaching materials and preparation of educators to address this issue. However, the first step is to begin the process of decolonizing behavior and stereotyped beliefs and, above all, to reconfigure and diversify the school curriculum.

So, in answer to the research's guiding question: Could Pretagogy be a mechanism for combating racism in dance classes in the school environment? We affirm that blackgogy can be an effective mechanism for combating racism in dance classes in the school

environment. Since it emerges as a support for educators in dance classes, putting into practice an anti-racist, multicultural and empowering pedagogy, which works on ethnic-racial relations through its own educational practices, such as the "Markers of Africanities", which favored a rapprochement with the children and sensitively boosted historical-cultural self-recognition in the face of each individual's narratives. In addition, the operative concepts used as theoretical-methodological support allowed the exploration of transversality in relation to experiences and nationalities.

When it comes to the curriculum and its relationship with the guidelines, it's not just about replacing the old with the new in the name of the subjects, but about valuing the experiences and history of the individual and their territory of origin. That's why it's important for educators to contextualize dance in dance classes so that children have access to their own culture.

This study reinforces the importance of rethinking Eurocentric thinking and applying Pretagogy as a pedagogical approach that combats racism in dance classes in the school environment. Through this approach, it is possible to work on ethnic-racial relations, promoting the valorization of Africanities and boosting students' historical-cultural self-recognition. In addition, it is important to direct research towards the initial training of teachers, in order to analyze the effects that this training has on the application of dance content in classes.

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